

SUCCESSFUL YOUNG SCHOOL PRINCIPALS FROM IP FAMILIES: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Abstract: This qualitative multiple case study aims to provide an in-depth understanding and analysis of success, experienced by young IP school principals. An in-depth interview with the participants was conducted with four young principals of different tribes ages 30 and below to learn about their cases and the significance of their career histories. The data were transcribed and analyzed using thematic content analysis and cross-case analysis. Difficulties and Hardships Endured, Challenges Surmounted and Fruits of Success were among the three main themes wherein each one encompassed the other themes that emerged. The results were presented and discussed within the context of the existing literature on career theory, indigenous epistemology, and social setting. These results helped in understanding the cases of young indigenous school principals and hopefully helped the educational institutions to be instruments in upholding the IP learners' right to increase their educational participation.

Keywords: Education, success, young IP principals, multiples case study, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Will your fingers be enough to count to get you at the finish line of your goal? Success may be easy for one to reach but not everybody. The truth about Indigenous People's success may give you information to reach your highest potential and be fulfilled.

Indigenous peoples are the first dwellers of their lands but are often poorly served by the education systems in their countries. Indigenous students are more likely to arrive at school hungry, ill, tired, and often bullied. Ethnic and cultural discrimination at schools are the major obstacles to equal access to education, causing poor performance and higher dropout rates. Indigenous students frequently find that the education offered by the state promotes individualism and a competitive environment rather than communal ways of life and cooperation. They are not taught relevant survival skills suitable for indigenous economies. They often come back to their communities with a degree that is irrelevant or unsuitable for their needs (Comfort, 2021; Cheromiah, 2021; Mishina, 2017; Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2017; Bodkin-Andrews and Carlson, 2016.)

Moreover, education is one of the best long-term financial and social assets the countries can make. Suitable education enables indigenous children and adult learners to exercise and enjoy economic, social, and cultural rights. Education is, therefore, an essential means for the enjoyment, maintenance, and transmission of indigenous cultures, languages, traditions, and traditional knowledge, as well as a vehicle for individual empowerment and agency. Learning from examples of success can enable systems and schools to do better and accelerate improvements for Indigenous students. An OECD report, "Promising Practices in Supporting Success for

Indigenous Students," highlighted the example of Indigenous students' success and how these successes were achieved (Commonwealth of Australia, 2017; Page, Trudgett, Bodkin-Andrews, 2019; Cosentino, 2016; Schleicher, 2017).

In the Philippines, there is an estimated 14 to 17 million Indigenous Peoples (IPs) belonging to 110 ethnolinguistic groups, mainly dwell in Northern Luzon (Cordillera Administrative Region, 33%) and Mindanao (61%), with some groups in the Visayas area. In recognition of ethnic diversities under the framework of national unity and development, the Philippine Constitution mandated the state to recognize, to protect, to promote, and to fulfill the rights of the Indigenous People. At present, little awareness has been paid to the positive effect of success stories in employment to address the low literacy rates of IPs, specifically in the Sarangani Province, Region XII (Avergonzado, 2016; Valdeavilla, 2018; Episcopal Commission on Indigenous People, 2017).

Thus, at this juncture, the voices of our successful indigenous principals have to be heard and be given importance. This paper presented the cases of the young school principals from IP families. What made them successful and better individuals would be a mirror to the young indigenous generation and other indigenous professionals. These would increase the Indigenous People's educational participation and educational success. To provide a better understanding of the term "principal," it is translated in the participants' respective dialects, as follows: Magpaulnauhay (Tagakaulo), Malak (T'boli), Gumdata did Gusatdo (Blaan), and Kalangkawan (Manobo).

1.1 Purpose of the Study

This study aimed to provide an in-depth understanding and analysis of successful young school principals from the IP families and explore in detail their successes.

Likewise, this research focused on the successful young indigenous school principals. The term 'indigenous' had been used throughout this paper, except when drawing on the work of others, the original terminology remained. The terms 'successful principals' refer to the teachers who had been recognized to have successive promotions and appointed as school principals by passing the principal's examination. On the other hand, the term 'young' is tagged to school principals who have reached as early as thirty and below. The researcher translated the participants' answers using their mother tongue to preserve and promote their culture and heritage being communicated through their native languages (Burrow-Goldhahn, 2018; Truong Hallinger and Sanga, 2017).

1.2 Research Questions

This study sought to answer the question:

1. How does the success of the participants be described?

1.3 Theoretical Lens

This study was based on the following theories; Human Capital Theory, Social Capital Theory, and Social Cognitive Career Theory.

Human Capital Theory

The theory proposed that individuals who invested in themselves, for instance, by enhancing their education and training, would be rewarded by achieving positive career outcomes, such as increased salary. Typical measures of human capital included the level of education educational quality, such as the prestige of the university or school attended, job tenure, and amount of training. It was found in a meta-analysis that the human capital measured hours worked, job and organizational tenure, work experience, and willingness to transfer. Hence, education levels were all positively associated with salary, promotions, and career satisfaction (Becker, 1999 as cited in Ishak, 2016; Ismail and Awang, 2017; Marginson, 2019; Hung and Ramsden, 2021; Holden and Biddle, 2017; Judge, Klinger, and Simon, 2010, as cited in Ishak, 2016).

Social Capital Theory

Social capital is defined as a function of social structures that facilitated the actions of individuals or as "an individual's network and elite institutional affiliation." Most definitions of social capital refer to the social resources available to an individual; in the context of organizations, these are the network of relationships between peers, supervisors, and subordinates. Social capital theory suggested that individuals who could build and mobilize their social capital would achieve greater levels of career success. This theory has two areas of social capital research that have paid significant attention to ethnicity: informal networks and mentoring relationships. (Duarte, Seng, and O'Brien, 2020; June Anderson,

Drechsler, Hessenauer, and Clark, 2019; Derik, 2018; Coleman, 1990, as cited in Ishak, 2016; Martin, Stefl, Cain, and Pfirman, 2020; Song, 2020; Kwang, and Sohn, 2018; Hayes, 2000, as cited in Ishak, 2016).

Social Cognitive Career Theory

SCCT stresses three social-cognitive processes considered to function concerning professional development and behavior: self-efficacy beliefs, result expectancies, and goal mechanisms. It was proposed by Lent, Brown, and Hackett and was drawn from general social cognitive theory. SCCT also focuses on how these mechanisms interconnected with another person (e.g., race/ethnicity), contextual (e.g., support system), and experiential/learning (e.g., access to educational resources) factors. Researchers who worked from this perspective have examined how social factors such as race, culture, ethnicity, and gender affect career self-efficacy beliefs and outcome expectations. In which it turned that they were hypothesized to determine career interests, goals, and ultimately career behavior (Bandura's, 1986; as cited in Ishak, 2016; (Međugorac, Šverko, and Babarović, 2020; Chun-Chen, 2020; Roller, Lampley, Dillihunt, Michael, and Turner, 2018).

The second and the last theory offered a more significant number of studies that considered ethnicity. These theories were relevant to the aims of this study and could be combined as the basis for interpreting the results.

1.4 Delimitation and Limitations

The researcher included four participants in a one-on-one in-depth interview. They were young IP school principals from secondary and elementary schools in the Division of Sarangani. The data were gathered from four young school principals of different tribes to have more cases to study and a wide range of comparisons for evidence to be as solid and reliable as a multiple-study requires.

This study was primarily designed to explore the different experiences of young IP school principals on how they became successful in their careers. This study had narrowed findings not intended for generalization with the other research settings. It involved two young IP School Principals from different schools in the municipality of Maasim, one from Malungon and another one from Alabel, Sarangani Province.

A one-on-one online in-depth interviews where open-ended questions were asked to the participants to describe their experiences and perceptions of their success. The interview was recorded through audiotapes and varied experiences of the participants were clustered into themes for analysis and interpretation. They were given assurance of the confidentiality of information they provided, data pseudonymization was implemented conforming appropriate ethical principles.

2. METHOD

2.1 Research Design

The methodology of this inquiry was a qualitative multiple-case study design. Qualitative in the sense that its research processes allowed the participants to voice their own career achievements, that is, their successes and challenges from their own perspectives. Their voices would provide a more detailed description of the meaning of their own career success. Likewise, the inductive processes of qualitative research allowed the researcher to review the participants' cases and to make connections by comparing the similarities and differences of their responses. With these, the proponent would be able to identify the common themes emerged (Creswell, 2013; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015, as cited in DeVore-Wedding, 2017; Harrison, Birks, Franklin, and Mills, 2017).

On the other hand, case study research is defined as a qualitative approach in which the investigator discovered a bounded system (a case) or multiple bounded systems (cases) over time through detailed, in-depth data collection concerning various sources of information. It reported a case description and case-based themes" (p. 73). It allowed comparisons between cases and individuals, allowed for exploring existing theories from the data (lessening the impact of preconceived ideas), and allowed the researcher to examine existing and new data in the form of artifacts, questionnaires, and interviews. Therefore, the researcher has to consider if it is wise to make a single case study or if it is wiser to make a multiple case study to understand the phenomenon (Wodon and Cosentino, 2019; Marrero Colon, 2019; Fishman, 2017).

However, multi-case designs are time-consuming and monetarily intensive, making them beyond the scope of novice and student-researchers. A two-case study is better than a one-case study when faced with a decision. The analytic benefits are much more excellent, and generalizability has expanded if the conclusions are similar. A system of multiple case studies, moreover, includes different locations, participants, or time-frame, which enhances the robustness of the study (Yin, 2009 as cited in Krusenvik, 2017; Lusua, 2019; Kornbluh, 2020; Sideri, Filippopoulou, Kalloniatis, and Gritzalis, 2019).

Thus, the participants in this study were the IP school principals from the different schools in the seven municipalities of Sarangani Province with ten years and below in the teaching profession.

Following the qualitative research design, the proponent was incorporating multiple-case studies and interviewing approaches. The researcher conducted a one-on-one interview to explore the participants' responses and she gathered more reliable information for validity to avoid biases. These then followed with the analyses of data. The unit of analysis was the individual IP school principal in each case. Transparency was maintained throughout the study, from data collection to interpretation and reporting, vital to measuring authenticity.

The participants of this study came from the different tribes with different individual experiences of struggles and had personal strategies of reaching success in their career. Thus, a qualitative multiple-case study was employed because it was deemed appropriate to use in this research.

2.2 Researcher's Role and Potential Ethical Issues

As the researcher of this study, I only focused on the cases of the successful young school principals from the IP families. I aimed to access the thoughts and feelings of my participants. The researcher's role in this qualitative research was critical as she collected the data and implemented the analysis. To come up with satisfying results, particularly in the validity and reliability of my study, the succeeding steps were followed: First, in selecting the participants, I asked the help of the In-Charge of DepEd Planning and Research Unit Office in Sarangani to ensure my participants' accurate profile stipulated in the inclusion criteria (Gallis, Maselko, O'Donnell, Song, Saqib, Turner, and Sikander, 2018; Glogowski, 2016).

However, all investigators researching with human participants must observe the legal and ethical responsibilities set forth by the Common Rule and the standards of Institutional Review Boards (IRBs), such as obtaining informed consent to ensure the research risks which will be proportionate to the expected benefits that minimize the risks. So, the researcher sent an invitation letter and a signed consent form to each participant. Next, before the conduct of interviews via messenger smartphone app and direct phone calls, I conducted a self-assessment of my competence to ensure my competence in doing this endeavor. Then I sought help from the experts who had already conducted interviews (Hsiao, 2021; Baumgartner, 2021).

After that, I had a few practice interviews before the presence of my thesis adviser for him to critique me. On the scheduled interviews, I conducted it following the design like establishing a good rapport with my participants and giving them sufficient time to tell their stories and provide the necessary information I needed. All data collected were kept confidential. All personal information was coded. The participants were assigned corresponding pseudonyms to hide their individual identification. Transparency on the researcher's part contributed to the validity of the research, data collection, analysis, and interpretation. Thus, during the interpretations and analyses of data, I ensured that my experiences and personal views definitely would not affect the participants' responses. The procedure of member checking was also used to control biases (Bayad, Elbir, Topbaş, Kocabaş, and Aydemir, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015).

2.3 Sample and Site

From a pool of school principals in the Division of Sarangani, four young school principals were selected as participants based on the following initial criteria: A male or female school principal from indigenous families. They are 30 years old and below and ten years and below in the service from a classroom teacher to their present position as school principals.

The researcher included four participants in a one-on-one in-depth interview to have more cases to study and a wide range of comparisons for evidence to be as solid and reliable as a multiple-study requires. They were young IP school principals from secondary and elementary schools in the Division of Sarangani. Also, they were identified using maximum purposive sampling, otherwise known as heterogeneous purposive sampling.

The results from purposive sampling do not always have to be statistically representative of the more significant population of interest, yet these may be used in a wide range of situations. The more prior information the researchers have about their particular communities of interest, the better the sample they will get (Onwuegbuzie, and Collins, 2017; Foley, 2018; Kudliskis, 2019).

Thus, heterogeneous purposive sampling was the technique being used by the researcher in this study for her to gain much insight from the diverse range of cases. The researcher verified the complete qualification details of the participants from the records of the planning office of the Division Sarangani to ensure accurate and honest information being provided by individual participants.

2.4 Access and Permission

Furthermore, she did further planning, and outlined protocol for her to be guided in this project. She explained the risks and the benefits to the participants before they decided to participate in this endeavor. They were made aware of the research topic, the sorts of questions they were asked, and the process of storing and using the data. To protect privacy and confidentiality, data pseudonymization was implemented. The proponent was mindful to keep the data confidential. Conforming to this policy, the participants were informed. They were given assurance of the confidentiality of information that they would provide. In addition, their permission to videotape or audiotape the interview was also requested (Cunha, 2018; Glover, 2021).

Likewise, during the actual interview process, the researcher established a rapport with the participants and encouraged them to participate in the conversation. Being at ease is essential for data gathering quality and for helping the interviewees answer the questions honestly and openly. They strictly followed the agreed time for the start and end of the interview. The researcher avoided pitfalls like correcting, educating, and counseling the participants. In qualitative research, validity relates to the honesty and genuineness of the research data. During the processes of data analyses, the researcher ensured that there were no biases, like classifying the data into themes or categories. Since the study was a multiple-case, cross-case synthesis was also applied in data analyses, one of the suggested analytic strategies (Gordon, 2018; Ridder, 2017).

Hence, researchers need to be fully aware of the obstacles in their research and plan for preventative action, as this may affect the timing of the study. The participants were from the different cultures, yet the researcher expected them to be well-adjusted and broad-minded. Still, as the researcher, I was very cautious about their sensitivity to some issues. With this in mind, the questions were carefully developed and made. No biases prevailed and the participants were open to the process of listening and understanding the issues.

2.5 Data Gathering Strategies

The primary data in qualitative research is the participants' thoughts, ideas, and impressions. Case studies make extensive use of qualitative data. Descriptions, quotations, and excerpts are raw data from the empirical world that provide breadth and detail. In a qualitative case study, the commitment to be factual and descriptive constitutes a significant commitment to representing the participants on their terms. Interviews are an essential feature of case study research design. Interviews provide each participant's lived career histories, perspectives, and nuances. Thus, this study employed a one-on-one interview to collect necessary data from the participants. Due to the pandemic's travel restrictions and the distance of some participants, the face-to-face interview procedure was not made possible. The interview was done online using the messenger application, readily available on smartphones. She did interviews with her participants through direct phone calls especially for those who did not have an internet connection. She followed the format and protocols for the interviews with examples given. The semi-structured interviews were carried out approximately an hour or less than an hour (Gustafsson, 2017; DeVore-Wedding, 2017). Moreover, the time given to each of the participants helped me establish a relationship with them and allowed me to explore their beliefs and perceptions about the success of their careers. Questions prompted the participants to indicate their education level and years of teaching experience. Open-ended questions were asked to the participants to describe their experiences and perceptions of their success. The interview was recorded through audiotapes and I transcribed the participants' responses. As the researcher, I analyzed the transcribed data and referred them to a professional data analyst for thorough analyses and interpretations.

2.6 Data Analysis Approach

When conducting case studies, the data collection and analysis usually occur synchronously. Data analysis involves examining, categorizing, tabulating, testing, or combining quantitative and qualitative evidence. The type of case study determines the sort of analysis being used. There are five techniques for analysis: pattern matching, explanation building, time-series analysis, logic models, and cross-case analysis (Gustafsson, 2017; Kalu and Norman, 2018).

The researcher preferred to analyze the data collected using qualitative analysis and the analytic technique of multiple cases. Research began with the first interview, observation, and document read. Writing notes, generating codes from the data, cross-comparing the codes to draw comparisons and themes, pattern matching, and cross-comparing the cases are analytical tactics employed during and after data gathering. It is, therefore, the first step in data analysis (Corbin and Strauss, 2008 cited in Levings, 2015).

Another thing to consider is pattern matching. It is an intuitive process that occurs when codes are developed or after themes have emerged. Patterns are characterized by "similarity, frequency, sequence, correspondence or causation." Cross-case

synthesis aids the researcher in understanding the difference and similarities between the cases to make assertions about the cases being studied. She compared themes between the cases with the research questions. These strategies assisted her in identifying codes, themes, patterns, and relationships between each data source. She used the information to cross-compare the results of these strategies between the courses (Leavy, 2017; Kothari, 2019).

Specifically, the analysis included creating memos, developing and refining codes, identifying patterns through creating tables, and identifying themes from the codes and designs. A memorandum was made for each interview, including a brief overview and the researcher's initial reactions.

Also, the open-ended survey question responses were coded and written in the tables. These codes were also cross-compared with interview codes, adding more data and verification to the coding scheme. These also created data tables for each case consisting of interview questions, survey data, and research question responses by each participant to find patterns across the data. These proved data tables were helpful to refine and verify codes for each research question. Codes were then clustered to create the emergent themes. Quotes representing each theme were copied from the transcripts and compiled into separate documents by article for further review. The expert validated my choice of themes and reviewed the sections to verify these premise reflections I formulated (Kalu and Norman, 2018; Andersen, Dubois, and Frida, 2018; Levings, 2015).

Likewise, enhancing the trustworthiness and rigors of the study, the researcher considered the internal and external validity. Internal validity involves establishing a causal relationship, whereby certain conditions lead to other states, as distinguished from spurious associations. Tactics that increase internal validity include pattern matching. This logic compares the empirically based pattern with a predicted one; if the conventions coincide, the results strengthen the internal validity of the qualitative case study. To refrain from biases, the researcher applied the systematic data analysis strategy like multiple viewings of videotaped and audiotaped data (Neufeld, Chapman, Crier, Marsh, McLeod, and Deane, 2019; Sorin-Peters, 2015).

Hence, reliability involves demonstrating the operations of the study, such as the data collection procedures that can repeat with the same results. Reliability can be increased by documenting processes in detail. However, it is not easy to achieve reliability in the traditional sense in qualitative case study research because the information gathered is highly contextual and a function of how well skilled the researcher is getting it (Kärner and Höning, 2021).

Before the analysis, I also reviewed the transcripts to prevent any content error. Lastly, themes were made possible that these were consistent across all data being gathered. So, she did cross-checking and made accurate notes about the definitions of all themes derived.

3. RESULT

This part presents the findings, the description of the individuals, the analyses of the themes, and the utilization of the cross-case analysis as the design of the study.

The participants of this study were the young IP school principals with their corresponding chosen pseudonyms based on their cultural group identities namely: Kagan, a substitute name of Tagakaulo tribe in which they are recognized by their fitting suits of red and yellow striped clothes; Ikat, the Tboli tribe's identity as a well-known weaver; To Lagad, refers to Blaan's geophysical location of the village which means the highland area; Ulaging, the Manobo tribe's identity which refers to their sacred epic.

The analyses of themes of the cases among successful young IP school principals, focused to the study on their difficulties, hardships, challenges surmounted, and fruits of success. Each main theme consists of two clustered themes and are further analyzed through a cross-case analysis.

From the findings of the study, which were based from the participants' responses of the in-depth interview on how they describe their individual success, the following cases are revealed.

The participants encountered difficulties and hardships in the beginning of their journey, this main theme is classified into two clustered themes which are personal battles and environmental factors. It is concluded from the general responses of the participants revealed that self-doubt and difficult terrain were the barriers in performing their tasks and in reporting to their individual station.

Another problem in achieving success are the challenges that they were able to surmount. This main theme was clustered into two themes specifically: community support and internal arsenal. The participants declared that family support and learning from others helped them overcome obstacles while conquering fears and doubts, working hard, understanding others, and patience and dedication were the strategies in reaping the fruit of success.

After all, was enjoying the moment of glory. The fruits of success were consisting of two clustered themes namely: emotional impact and cultural impact. The feeling of fulfillment increased their faith and motivation, dignity and confidence which also served as their legacy to their tribes and inspired them to enhance their professional development to achieve their future dreams.

4. DISCUSSION

This part presents the discussion of major findings, comparisons of findings to other existing literature, limitations, and overall significance of the study. Moreover, this study sought to explore the different cases of young IP school principals from the seven other municipalities of Sarangani Province utilizing a multiple case study.

4.1 Major Findings

After an in-depth analyses of the data gathered, the following findings were drawn:

It was revealed that there were experiences of the young IP school principals that made them successful in their careers.

Difficulties and Hardships endured by the Young IP School Principals

Young school principals had less professional but more ideological, social, and digital skills. Identically, the principals were the second most significant school-related factor in affecting student achievement, behind instructors, accounting for around a quarter of overall school impacts. Nevertheless, a life's experience had run into a young aboriginal's life that made them succeed in her chosen career path. The IP, in general, was usually seen as backward and belonging to the past. Their knowledge and skills were considered inferior or invalid compared to 'modern' knowledge and skills. When discussing indigenous life, there is a tendency to misrepresent or misinterpret them because of the prevailing prejudice (Marzano, Waters, and McNulty, 2005, as cited in Sherlock, 2020; Feminella, 2020; Berry, 2018; Soto and Deemer, 2018).

Moreover, these experiences of the young IP school principals had been through before realizing their attainment. Some difficulties and hardships clustered into personal battles and environmental factors. For personal conflicts, they went through self-doubt and became ideal. There were experiences passing through rugged terrain and dealing with other people's cultures (Whitley, Beauchamp, and Brown, 2021; Ismail, and Rishani, 2018, Stout, 2017).

Similarly, newly installed school principals usually experienced self-doubt due to having little knowledge or experience handling school movement and teachers, parents, students, and the community. They felt the pressure of meeting the expectations of the community.

Also, the feeling of self-doubt and anxiety was due to the new leader's inexperience and lack of understanding of the demands of school leadership. Adding to this self-doubt was new school leaders' pressure to meet contract performance measures to remain open to serving students. To address this issue, it was suggested that mentor support in this area was nonexistent unless the school principal asked for help (Wright, Kacmarski, Firsick, Jenkins-Guarnieri, and Kimm, 2020; Giraud, Bernard, and Trinchera, 2019).

The young principals were more likely optimistic in viewing themselves handling a school. It was emphasized that leading people and involving both internal and external stakeholders according to a fixed plan or system effectively resulted. Most commonly, young principals applied the learnings gained from college and during the master's course. What was learned was included in the different leadership styles from a theory and then used it into practice. Education aims to identify and develop each person's unique potential and absolute moral excellence to serve society better. Character is formed by emulating the role models and heroes (Alayoubi, Al Shobaki, and Abu-Naser, 2020; Carter, 2019; Mahmood, 2017).

Under environmental factors is the difficulty of the terrain accessing the location of the stationed school. It has been a problem since then. Few rivers cross strong currents, particularly during the rainy season. There were mountains to walk through with slippery roads. To address the said problem, planners for school development should also aim to improve equity in access. While access for students, teachers, and community members with disabilities is usually enshrined in the law, this does not imply that it is always followed, reinforcing inequity. Rural areas with low population density and rugged

terrain present a challenge that needs to be resolved at the micro-planning level, looking specifically for an efficient operation of the whole municipal planning system (Barrett, 2019; Foster, 2019; McGee, 2018).

Meanwhile, educational delivery mechanisms in higher education, colleges, and universities across the globe ventured into different practices such as distance education, online teaching, remote learning, blended learning, and mobile learning. These learning modalities do not mean going away from the traditional arrangement of the instructional process or creating an entirely new educational system. It provides a temporary feasible alternative for education practitioners to perform instruction and provide students with necessary instructional support (Hodges, 2020; Rotas and Cahapay, 2020; Corley, Reeves, and Odera, 2020; Scott, and Sharp, 2019).

It can be hard when a specific individual deals with other people's cultures. It needs to consider the age of the people to deal with. There are also people, especially teachers, who lack dedication. It can be proven by the number of days attended in school. Like members of most organizations, teachers shape their beliefs and actions mainly in conformance with the everyday world's structures, policies, and traditions. To consider the teacher's school station has a rugged terrain and is situated in the far-flung area (Rosenholtz, 1991 cited in Campbell, 2017; Lariosa; 2020).

Challenges Surmounted by Young IP School Principals

In community support, this includes family support. In the Philippines setting, family support has been traditionally observed. It does play a significant role for a child to achieve his dream. To gain support from an IP family is already substantial enough to sustain and survive getting an education and even higher.

Additionally, family relationships and support are enduring consequences for well-being across an individual's life course. For better or worse, family ties play a critical part in molding an individual's well-being throughout their lives. Given that these four participants came from an IP family, their families thought carefully about the importance of acquiring education and finishing a degree. Some IPs viewed education as an essential tool to improve their situation by pursuing economic, social, and cultural development; it provided individual empowerment and self-determination (Perry, and Geller, 2021; Crews, 2019; Forster, 2019; Samanta, 2018; Regaspi, 2017).

Parent-family engagement is widely understood as an essential factor in one's child's school experiences and educational outcomes. Thus, family involvement influences how a successful individual may become and realize who and what an individual is made of. The family can inculcate the love to lifelong learning and not merely finishing a simple task (Carter, 2019; Flores, Morgan, Rivera, and Clark, 2019; Wright, Kacmarski, Firsick, Jenkins-Guarnieri, & Kimm, 2020).

Learning from others can be considered a community support. There is a sign of learning and educating oneself to become proficient in education. Additionally, reading more and studying some successful stories of past administrators could help gain relevant insights. Besides that, seeking help and advice from the past administrators and experienced principals could also be a great help in assessing what matters in regards to running a school. Hence, these learnings could help strategize plans, programs, and projects for the betterment of the school and the environment. Leadership and learning are mutually beneficial (Luedke, 2020; Chirgwin, Farago, d'Antione, and Nagle, 2017; Small, 2017).

In addition, a growth mindset could be associated with resilience to challenges and failure. It showed a greater appeal for learning for its purpose and higher essential motivation. Self-doubt about one's competence would appear harmful to establishing a growth mindset and complicated generating feelings of crucial reason. By definition, self-doubt is the attention given to one's self. This focus on "hesitation" and "uncertainty" and measuring oneself rather than fully engaging in tasks in an unselfconscious way or a specific individual lacks conviction. Self-doubt could be a mental illness, and the only cure for it is to have the guts to get started (Berlin, 2019; Shiu, 2017; Gerstner, 2017).

Based on the interview, it was viewed that working hard is essential in achieving a specific goal. The toxic school culture could poison the school work environment. The lack of shared purpose or a splintered mission based on teacher's self-interest, norms of radical individualism, the acceptance of mediocrity, and the presence of the avoidance of innovation manifested during the interviews. All of these could drain energy, but by diverting the focus to the school's core mission by working diligently and living example little by little, these individuals would become someone who actively contributed to their own success or improvement. Teachers should work for a standard plan and avoid hidden agenda, which would mean that common goals should drive them rather than their personal interests.

Moreover, hard work for career progression means having the capability and efficacy to attain the career objective. There were critical elements of work capability/effectiveness such as the required knowledge and skills, ability to pursue, putting

in the effort, pushing through, the dedication of time and resource toward achieving a goal, and pushing through until the desired target had been realized. Being a hardworking individual is to have the ability to set goals and pursue them without getting distracted till it is achieved at the end (Asumeng and Assan 2015; Michel and Hargis, 2017; Giraud, Bernard, and Trinchera, 2019).

On the other hand, there is a need for a leader to have a heart, be passionate, and with intense dedication. It takes commitment and working hard to improve oneself constantly. Hardworking means commitment and dedication to achieving organizational goals, and an individual should blend his personal and corporate objectives to achieve a common goal (Giraud, Bernard, and Trinchera, 2019; Ismail, and Rishani, 2018; Asumeng and Assan, 2015). Furthermore, working hard and seeking enlightenment from God could impact in achieving goals and success. Hard work and dedication yielded results. With the guidance of God, surely He would provide a greater opportunity for one to succeed. Although, no study directly stated about the connection of Divine Providence and landing into our chosen career. In addition, getting into the right job or career is not God's most significant concern, but that does not mean He is of no concern. The outstanding work of the Holy Spirit is to guide and empower people for the life and career to which God leads them. In a particular verse found in 1st Corinthians 12:7-10, "but now the Spirit routinely guides believers to particular works and gives them the skills they need." This proves that the Holy Spirit is guiding what kind of work people do and how to do that work (Cech, Metz, Smith, and DeVries, 2017; Henson, 2018).

Apart from surmounting challenges is to enlighten oneself to understand others and understand one's culture and attitude. As a leader leads his group and being an IP leader, there were a few difficulties encountered such as: lack of dedication of teachers, the financial difficulty of teachers, parent-teacher relationship. After all, it would be getting better by being friendly to all, with co-teachers, to the community. One should use heart in leading the people. By using heart, it could be easy to consider their mistakes and inspire them to do right.

Awareness and understanding of one's emotions could support leaders' efforts to develop self-understanding and strengthen relationships with others, contributing to the growth and improved communication. Thus, understanding one's feelings or others is a critical leadership skill (Patti, 2015; Wang, 2018).

Above all, having patience and dedication towards the environment and surroundings could help surmount challenges. To succeed, one must be patient and be dedicated. He seeks an occupation and pursues higher education, and works harder for his dream. Life is full of challenges, but it is fulfilling. Indeed, one can succeed regardless of their race or tribe. Although it will take time, one's patience along with his dedication and diligence, for a goal to be met it will surely come to pass (Meigs 2018; Serra, Psarra, and O'Brien, 2018; Kudiskis, 2019; Sherlock, 2020).

Moreover, when it comes to patience and dedication, it has been said that dedication to being an instructional leader, governed by her inner commitment to foster teaching and learning within her community and family is vitally important. Additionally, building relationships with the bosses and colleagues, being accountable for the learning atmosphere of the school and influencing any organization through action and examples, data-driven decisions, facilitating job-embedded learning, and championing teacher excellence are equally important. It is also significant to enhance the learning process, academic achievement, and programs essential for the students to attain optimal personal growth and acquire positive social skills and values.

Likewise, one of the best qualities of a good school principal is dedication. A competent school administrator must be committed to the institution. They must make all decisions in the best interests of the students. The principal must embody the school spirit and tone. The learners need evidence that the school principal loves the school by being around and highly visible; that he has their best interests at her heart (Kelly, 2020; Wang, Pollock, and Hauseman, 2018; Schleicher, 2017).

Fruits of Success as Relished by Young IP School Principals

There is a proverb that goes like this. "Success is that moment in time when you are enjoying the fruits of your labor." At this part, the participants had relished the fruits of their success as they shared their experiences. There was an emotional impact: satisfaction/fulfillment. It was undeniable that most people encountered hardships in life, especially those who aimed high. With this, being an IP principals, success for them is fulfilling. The hardships they experienced during the years of pursuing their degrees was discrimination.

Additionally, job satisfaction is defined as the sense of fulfillment brought about by a feeling of achievement and recognition. When people do or perform a specific duty or work, they do it well since they know there is a clear expectation

of a reward for the job well-done. Undoubtedly, conquering hardships resulting in fulfillment and the succession of position title is worth rewarding (Ismail, and Rishani, 2018; Chirgwin, Farago, d'Antione, and Nagle, 2017; Maforah, 2015).

Similarly, success is defined as tomorrow's reflection by the result of the things done from the past and present. In particular, one must create something that contributes to one's satisfaction in life. There is a famous quote and I quote: "Always ask yourself if you are doing today is getting closer to where you want to be tomorrow." It implies that one must do well things right now and do plan to have a great result in the future (Patti, Senge, Madrazo, and Stern, 2015; Wu, Low, Tan, Lopez, and Liaw, 2015; Felt, 2017; White, 2019).

Different people provide different meanings to the outcomes or results of their work. Some may consider it a means of getting pay, while others think of it as a status classification that promotes a successful career. Conversely, others view their work as a calling, and it is fulfilling (Haar, Roche, and Brougham, 2019; Shiu, 2017; Samantha, 2018; Bellah, 2015).

It adds up that everything is difficult, but by having a heart full of perseverance and compassion, everything seems light to the feeling of young IP principals. It is emphasized that work has become a focal area in providing meaning, stability, and a sense of community and identity in people's lives (Cartwright and Holmes, 2016; Crews, 2019; Lariosa, 2020; Corley, Reeves, and Odera, 2020; Wright, Kacmarski, Firsick-Guarnieri, and Kimm, 2020).

Faith can have a different meaning to another. The term "faith" has a wide range of meanings, ranging from a general religious attitude to personal acceptance of a specific set of ideas. In addition to the definition of faith, it is relational, implying the trust of one upon another. It is also seeing and knowing and is further discussed that learning occurs when an active knower interacts with a dynamic world of persons and objects, meeting its unshaped or unorganized stimuli with the ordering organizing power of the knower's mind (Buss, Erbacher, Kryzanowski, Pisca, and Bellefeuille, 2020; Palframan, 2021; Mambo, 2019; Meigs, 2018).

Moreover, these challenges motivated me to pursue more in my career. The success was not only for him but for the community where he belongs. Also, it is described that motivation is a straightforward set of goals, plan, and a step that requires achieving and implementing that plan effectively.

The participants were motivated due to their desire to achieve their goals. This career motivation has a relationship to self-efficacy and career success. As reflected in Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT), inspiration can be intrinsic or extrinsic. In the case of To Lagad and Ulaging, the sources of their motivations could likely be indifferent. They wanted to pursue their career objectives: to be promoted to a higher position and earn money to support their family and the desire of helping people of the same culture (Day and Sammons, 2016; Forster, 2019; Scott, and Sharp, 2019).

Furthermore, other people viewed success differently. Success usually refers to any positive results associated with wealth and status in society. Success may come in different forms. It is also launching the right job and experiencing joy while doing it. A participant emphasized that he could confidently give his best efforts and assurance of the results because he liked what he was doing. Among leadership scholars and practitioners, self-confidence is a characteristic widely believed to be necessary for effective leadership, and empirical research has repeatedly validated this belief.

Thus, good leadership and self-confidence are widely believed to be necessary for effective leadership. It is asserted that self-confidence is an essential trait of successful leadership. Confidence in leadership can also lead the school institution's progress. To do it successfully, it requires that the principals are confident in their ability to assess the quality and effectiveness of teachers and to take the necessary actions when instruction is weak (Kärner and Höning 2021; Bremond, 2017; Shiu, 2017; McGee, 2018).

Acceptance and respect by the community of the tribal governance work. One becomes a full-fledged bar by gaining the community's respect and exhibiting the capacity to lead. So as for Ulaging, success is more than reaching a goal. Moreover, it brings back to her dignity as a human being and gains her fellowmen's respect (Crews, 2019; Choudhry, Park, Golden, and Bokharey, 2017; Sharma and Phyak, 2017; Green, 2017; Domingo, 2016).

While the organizing principle in the society is kinship, communities are also linked through a recognized leader who does not command but whose word is respected because of his status, economic means, courage, skill in settling disputes, and wisdom in interpreting laws.

Lastly, it can be concluded that professional development in the fruits of success. It may be an opportunity to enhance skills and ability to handle school.

Based on the interview, there was a unison viewpoint on professional development among the participants. They were inclined to the idea of equipping themselves with more knowledge through professional development. In like manner, it was admittedly claimed that there was a need to acquire essential knowledge, especially in the implementation of the programs and projects of the department.

Also, just like teachers, instructional leaders must have professional development. It must be planned, long-term, embedded in their work-related tasks, focused on student achievement, supportive to the school staff, and observed reflective practice. Additionally, it needs to include opportunities to work, discuss, and solve problems with colleagues. Principals and aspiring principals have the chance to meet in settings to explore and reflect on current school and leadership topics (Haar, Roche, and Brougham, 2019; Mhlanga, 2017; Feminella, 2020).

Furthermore, a participant envisioned that she would become an excellent transformational leader in the next five years, helping to produce more IP professionals and aiming for a higher position in the future and be an inspiration to the Department of Education.

On the other hand, others were doing their best as administrators, abiding by all the programs and projects of the department. There was a clear view of innovations in the future.

Similarly, one also aims to become a district supervisor or an education program specialist.

Generally speaking, the participants had their clear views of the future and the future endeavors of their chosen career paths. However, young principals with no prior administrative experiences were considerably idealistic based on early leadership perspectives. Others who had previously held executive positions (e.g., teacher leader, officer-in-charge, etc.) voiced more realistic views. But they, too, believed that "things will be different when I am in control." (Staniland, Harris, and Pringle, 2020; Sideri, Kitsiou, Filippopoulou, Kalloniatis, and Gritzalis, 2019; Gentilucci, Denti, and Guaglianone, 2015).

By and large, young and new principals, even those whose previous experiences had prepared them well for the demands of site management, were typically upbeat about their chances of success.

4.2 Comparison of Findings with Existing Studies

Difficulties and Hardships endured by the Young IP School Principals

Based on the findings, these were experiences these young IP school principals had been through before realizing their attainment. Some difficulties and hardships clustered into personal battles and environmental factors. For personal conflicts, they went through self-doubt and became idealistic. There were experiences of passing through rugged terrain and dealing with other people's culture for the environmental factors.

Additionally, the self-doubt that a new school principals had experienced in her study was anxiety due to the new leader's inexperience and lack of understanding of the demands of school leadership. Adding to this self-doubt was new school leaders' pressure to meet contract performance measures to remain open to serving students. To address this issue, it was suggested that mentor support in this area was nonexistent unless the school principal asked for help (Fitzsimmons, 2020; Henkenberns, 2019; Dunford, 2019).

Next is idealism. Education seeks to uncover and develop each person's potential and absolute moral excellence to serve society better. To portray the latent forms or concepts in the mind, introspection, intuition, insight, and whole-part logic were utilized. Character is developed through imitating examples and heroes. Planners for school development should also aim to improve equity in access. They added that rural areas with low population density and rugged terrain present a challenge that needed to be resolved at the micro-planning level—and looking specifically for an efficient operation of the whole municipal planning system (transportation, communication, and accessibility (Hota, 2020; Barrett, 2019; Ilodigwe, 2018; Mayorga, 2020; Mahmood, 2017).

Likewise, members of most organizations, teachers primarily create their views and acts in response to the structures, regulations, and traditions of the workplace (Tessaro, Landertinger, and Restoule, 2021; Liu, Chang and Yen-Po, 2020; Campbell, 2017).

Challenges Surmounted by Young IP School Principals

Data gathered from the findings, were the challenges surmounted by these young IP school principals before realizing their attainments. In surmounting these challenges, there was a support from the community and an internal arsenal. For

community support, it came from the family and learning from others. There were conquering fears and doubts for the internal arsenal, working hard, understanding others, patience, and dedication.

Family relationships and support were enduring consequences for well-being across an individual's life course. For better or for worse, family ties have played a critical part in molding an individual's well-being throughout life. Given that these four participants came from IP families, their families thought carefully about the importance of acquiring education and finishing a degree. Some IPs viewed education as an essential tool to improve their situation by pursuing economic, social, and cultural development; it provided individual empowerment and self-determination (Khoo and Yoke, 2020; Fitzsimmons, 2020; Dunford, 2019; Forsters, 2019; Regaspi, 2017).

Moreover, parent-family engagement was widely understood as an essential factor in one's child's school experiences and educational outcomes. Thus, family involvement played how a successful individual had become and realized who and what an individual was made of. The family inculcated the love to lifelong learning and not merely finishing a simple task (Janson, 2020; Wright, Kacmarski, Firsick, Jenkins-Guarnieri, and Kimm, 2020, Flores, Morgan, Rivera, and Clark, 2019; Barr, 2015).

Additionally, reading more and studying some successful stories of past administrators could help to gain relevant insights. Besides that, seeking help and advice from past administration and experienced principals could also help assess what matters regarding how to run a school. Hence, these learnings could help strategize plans, programs, and projects for the betterment of the school and environment. As the former US president John F. Kennedy once said, "Leadership and learning are indispensable to each other."

However, a growth mindset could be associated with resilience to challenges and failure. It showed a greater appeal for learning for its purpose and higher essential motivation. Self-doubt about one's competence would appear harmful to establishing a growth mindset and complicated generating feelings of the important reason. By definition, self-doubt is the attention given to one's self. This focused on "hesitation" and "uncertainty" and measuring oneself rather than fully engaging in tasks in an unselfconscious way or a specific individual lacks conviction. Self-doubt can be a mental illness, and the only cure for it is to have the guts to get started. (Berlin, 2019; Espinal, 2021).

Moreover, hard work for career progression means having the capability and efficacy to attain the career objective. There are critical elements of work capability/effectiveness such as the required knowledge and skills, ability to pursue, putting in the effort, pushing through, the dedication of time and resource toward achieving a goal, and pushing through until the desired target is realized. Being a hardworking individual is to have the ability to set goals and pursue them without getting distracted until it is achieved in the end. Lastly, to work hard in an organization such as in school is to be able to meet all the expectations of the school organization and also goes the extra mile to do things that helps the organization (Asumeng and Assan 2015; Michel and Hargis, 2017; Giraud, Bernard, and Trinchera, 2019).

Hardworking means commitment and dedication to achieving organizational goals. An individual should blend his personal and corporate objectives to achieve a common goal written of the importance of spiritual renewal. Spiritual renewal plays a role in reconnecting with one's core values. Such practice helps educational leaders remove themselves from the often emotionally charged immediacy of daily problems and refocus energy toward one's mission. Thus, it emphasizes in the article that a good administrator must be devoted to the school and make decisions for the best interests of the students. A principal must embody the school spirit and tone. It needs to be evident to the learners that the school principal loves the school by being around and highly visible and having their best interests at heart. Nevertheless, this kind of dedication can be hard to maintain but results in enormous dividends for school staff, students, and society. Although expressed as distinct attributes, patience and commitment are interconnected, as they are concerned with school improvement and subject matter (White, 2019; Farmer, 2015; Kelly, 2020; Gustafson, 2019; Espinal, 2021).

Fruits of Success as Relished by Young IP School Principals

There is a proverb that says: "Success is that moment in time when you are enjoying the fruits of your labor." In relishing the fruits of success is vitally important to one's emotional and cultural impact. Emotional impact has satisfaction/fulfillment and increased faith and motivation. Cultural influence has dignity and confidence, legacy, and personal development.

Different people provided different meanings to the outcomes or results of their work. Some may consider it as a means of getting a pay. In contrast, others believe it is a classification of status, and others think it is a promotion leading to a

successful career. Conversely, others viewed their work as a calling, the work which is fulfilling (Wingerter, 2020; Burrow-Goldhahn, 2018, Bellah, 2015).

Above all, Instructional leadership plays a significant role in education reform. Much has been written in strategies for school improvement, and there is widespread agreement that the two need to be combined and synchronized. For the schools, success often depends on the motivations and actions of leaders at their school's level. With good leadership, self-confidence is widely believed to be necessary for effective leadership. Self-confidence is an essential trait of successful leadership. Confidence in leadership can also lead to the school institution's progress (Bremond, 2017; Felt, 2017; Fullan, 2015).

By and large, young and new principals, even those whose previous experiences had prepared them well for the demands of site management. They were typically upbeat about their opportunities to succeed.

4.3 Implications for Future Research

Finally, the results or findings of this study could not generate any generalization from the revealed experiences of the four participants for other concerned and relevant individuals. Hence, it was suggested that future studies related to this study be conducted to other research sites and to other purposively selected participants to validate and compare the significant results of the present investigation. Furthermore, some future researchers may conduct related studies to check if there are relevant changes among the participants' experiences on how they become successful in their careers.

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